

**USE OF UGC-INFONET CONSORTIUM IN RASHTRASANT TUKDOJI
MAHARAJ NAGPUR UNIVERSITY AND SANT GADGE BABA
AMRAVATI UNIVERSITY**

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Abstract

It mentions about use and facilities of UGC-Infonet digital library consortium in two universities of Vidarbha region in Maharashtra. Present research paper deals with information of consortia and its usages by faculty members, research scholars and post graduate students. Electronic journals bring new challenges for the library and information professionals to give full text access of scholarly publications in electronic version to its end users. Through UGC-Infonet digital library consortium access has been provided to large number of scholarly journals with assumption that broader, faster, better access makes more use of information.

Keywords: - *E-journals, e-resources, consortium, web based access, UGC-Infonet consortia.*

1. Introduction

The university grants commission (UGC) has initiated the UGC-Infonet program to provide electronic access to scholarly literature in all areas of learning to the university sector in India over internet. There are different sources such as guidance of the library professionals and teachers/guides, advertisements or through library orientation, the consortium known to the all faculty's users.

The government is also undertaking various steps to familiarize this facility in academic institutions for the advantage of research scholars. The university avails this facility and gain access to e-resources. UGC-Infonet is a program that provides electronic access to scholarly literature in all areas of learning to the universities in India. This program is wholly funded by the UGC and administered and monitored by INFLIBNET. Universities which are always lack of funds are

tremendously benefitted by this facility. UGC Infonet is an ambitious program of UGC to interlink all the universities in India with state of the art technology. This is wholly funded by the UGC. All universities eligible to receive grants under UGCs purview are the members of the program, and it will progressively be extended to the colleges.²

2. Definitions

Library cooperation is a social phenomenon by which libraries are mutually engaged to increase the service capabilities of a single library and by which the librarians extend their option to serve clients. It includes sharing materials or function or services that constitute a library system. A material includes both documentary and non-documentary forms. The function covers the activities concerning the acquisition, processing, storage etc.; include techniques, activities and procedures employed to establish contact between the document and its consumer i.e. lending, reference, documentation, translation, etc.¹

2.1. E-journals

Jones (W) in 1998 defined e-journals as “they are available electronically via a computer or computer network that they may or may not be published in some other (physical) medium, but that they are not in CD-ROM or diskettes. While some authors simply take an electronic journal as a publication whose primary means of delivery to subscribers is through a computer file. Electronic journals are counterpart of print journals which are browsed, viewed, searched and save using network computers. As far as access is concerned, electronic journals are the ideal solution for users. They permit full text access via computer terminals irrespective of location. No more user frustration because of non-availability of material on the shelf because of various reasons. An electronic version can be made available and accessible within minimum possible time.⁴

2.2. Library consortium

Allen and Hirshon have explained library consortium as “A generic term to

indicate any group of libraries that are working together towards a common goal, whether to expand co-operation or traditional library services (such as collection development) or electronic information services. It is now used broadly, libraries come together solely to achieve better pricing for purchasing electronic information.” According to Deng and Zou “A library consortium is an association of libraries established by formal agreement usually for the purpose of improving services through resource sharing among its members”.⁵

According to Webster’s third international dictionary “Library consortia is an agreement, combination or group formed to undertake an enterprise beyond the resources of any one member” (Merriam Webster online dictionary 2008)

Online dictionary for library and information science (ODLIS) defines “Library consortia as an association of independent libraries and/or library systems established by formal agreement, usually for the purpose of sharing”. Membership may be restricted to a specific geographical region, type of library (public, academic, special) or subject specialization”.

A consortium could describe as a group of organizations come together for fulfill a combined objective that usually requires cooperation and the sharing of resources. Moreover, need to have a clear mutual aim in order to ensure their success. The aim should be to deliver “more than the sum of the individual parts”. A library consortium creation can be local, regional, state, national and inter institutional level. Cooperative arrangements have been made among similar institutions to conduct business. Business means, collectively procuring electronic information resources and facilitate its wide access among its members.⁶

3. Types of consortia

By geographical area of coverage:

- 1) Local level consortia
- 2) Regional level consortia
- 3) State level consortia

- 4) National level consortia
- 5) International level consortia

4. UGC-Infonet consortium

UGC-Infonet digital library consortium is national level consortium for university and research institute libraries in India. It is expected to bring remarkable change in the academic set with the availability of e-resources access to scholars and academicians right on to their desktop. The goals through UGC Infonet to empower faculty and research students make the greatest use possible of an expanding access of information. This library consortium creates an opportunity to provide enhanced library services by making use of electronic resources, bibliographic databases and services offered through internet. The UGC-Infonet has brought a revolution in the service provision of university libraries in country, LIS professionals have naturally been attracted to know the use of the consortiums e-resources by the teachers, researchers and students. INFLIBNET center, the driving force behind the UGC-Infonet digital library consortium has been organizing an international conference-CALIBER (Convention on automation of libraries in education and research) every two years.⁸

5. Role of INFLIBNET

The INFLIBNET center acts as a nodal agency for implementation, monitoring and execution of the entire program through the committees mentioned above. It coordinates all activities concerned with negotiation, renewal of subscription of e-resources and subsequent trouble shooting on behalf of the consortium. The center also promotes cooperation amongst member universities and facilitates better terms of references for use and preservation of subscribed electronic resources.⁷ In brief, INFLIBNET is responsible for:

- Coordinating meetings of its committees;
- Constitution of negotiation committee through its governing board;
- Negotiating rates of subscription and its terms and conditions;

- Ensures IP-based access of subscribed e-resources to beneficiary universities;
- Attend to the problems faced by universities and liaise with publishers to resolve such problems;
- Develop tutorials and promotion materials, impart training and technical support to member universities;
- Propagate the consortium amongst other institutions so as to extend its benefits to other institutions by enrolling associate members;
- Evaluate subscribed e-resources and monitor its usage regularly;
- Signs license agreement for access to various electronic resources on behalf of members;
- Maintain and update website of the consortium;
- Organize awareness program to promote e-resources;
- Improve cooperation and communication amongst member universities;
- Measure impact of access to e-resources on research output in beneficiary universities; and
- Present periodic report to the UGC on extent of usage of e-resources, economics of the consortium and its impact on research output.

6. Role of UGC

The UGC-Infonet digital library consortium is fully funded by the university grants commission. The UGC is responsible for constituting the national steering committee of the consortium. The UGC is also responsible for making policies, monitoring the progress, coordinating with other consortium in the country and to ensure gradual decrease in subscription of print resources in the beneficiary institutions. The UGC also monitors usage of e-resources and its impact on research output in beneficiary universities.³

7. Objectives of the present study

- To identify importance regarding e-resources usage of UGC-Infonet digital

library consortium.

- To determine the use of UGC-Infonet consortium by the users in both universities.
- To spread awareness about the UGC-Infonet e-journals consortium and its sources.

8. Methodology

Descriptive methodology is used for the present study. Questionnaire is used as a technique to collect the primary related data from teachers, researchers and PG students. The researcher used descriptive method for the present research paper. Here an attempt has been made to present a way of process to the study keeping in mind objectives of the study a framework of UGC-Infonet digital library consortium users has been designed.

9. Sample population

Approximately 145 questionnaires were circulated in each university. But responses are 60 users from RashtrasantTukdojiMaharaj Nagpur University Nagpur and 61 users from SantGadge Baba Amravati University Amravati.

10. Use of UGC-Infonet e-resources in RashtrasantTukdojiMaharaj Nagpur University Nagpur

RashtrasantTukadojiMaharaj Nagpur University (RTMNU), formerly known as Nagpur University, is a public state university, established on 4 August 1923 in the city of Nagpur in Maharashtra state in central India. It has been accredited with the A grade by the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC)⁹

Following is the list of e-resources subscribed of UGC-Infonet digital library consortium by RashtrasantTukdojiMaharaj Nagpur University Nagpur.

Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University			
Sr. No.	Resource Name	Resource URL	No of Journals
1	American Chemical Society	http://pubs.acs.org/	50

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2	American Institute of Physics	http://journals.aip.org	18
3	American Physical Society	http://publish.aps.org/browse.php	13
4	Annual Reviews	http://arjournals.annualreviews.org/	33
5	Cambridge University Press	http://journals.cambridge.org/	224
6	Economic & Political Weekly	http://epw.in/	1
7	Emerald	http://www.emeraldinsight.com/	133
8	IEEE ASPP*	http://ueeexplore.ieee.org/	187
9	Institute of Physics	http://iopscience.iop.org/journals	46
10	ISID	http://isid.org.in/	Database
11	JCCC	http://jgateplus.com/	Database
12	JSTOR	http://www.jstor.org//	2500+
13	MathSciNet	http://www.ams.org/mathscinet	1 Database
14	Nature	http://www.nature.com/	1
15	Oxford University Press	http://www.oxfordjournals.org	262
16	Portland Press	http://www.portlandpress.com/	8
17	Project Euclid	http://projecteuclid.org	30
18	Project Muse	http://muse.jhu.edu/journals	500+
19	Royal Society of Chemistry	http://www.rsc.org/	29 + 6 Database
20	Science Direct (10 Subject Collection)	http://www.sciencedirect.com/	1036
21	Springer Link	http://link.springerlink.com/	1389+
22	Taylor & Francis	http://www.tandfonline.com/	1079
23	Wiley-Blackwell	http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/	908
24	Web of Science	http://www.webofknowledge.com/	Database

Table no. 01 List of e-resources

11. Use of UGC-Infonet e-resources in SantGadge Baba Amravati University Amravati

The university was established on 1 May 1983 through partitioning of the University of Nagpur. The university campus is spread over an area of 225 hectares, and the university is home to 20 post-graduate departments offering 25 courses in different disciplines. It has jurisdiction over five districts of Maharashtra: Akola, Amravati, Buldhana, Yavatmal, and Washim. Amravati

University is recognized under Section 12(B) of the University Grants Commission (UGC) Act of the Ministry of Education, Government of India. Amravati University is an associate member of the Association of Commonwealth Universities, London.¹⁰

11.1 Internet services of SantGadge Baba Amravati University Amravati

- 1) E-mail and internet services shall be provided for academic purposes only.
- 2) These services shall be provided to the following on priority basis as under:
 - i) Member 1 of the university authorities.
 - ii) Teaching departments of the university.
 - iii) Administrative section of the university.
 - iv) Post graduate teaching departments of affiliated colleges.
 - v) Affiliated colleges.
- 3) The minimum charges for internet services shall be Rs. 10/- for 30 minutes & Rs. 20/- for hour.
 - i) The internet e-mail services shall be provided free of cost to the faculty members/research students of the P.G. departments of the university for official use/ research / educational purpose on written recommendation of concerned H.O.D./ Principal.
 - ii) For print out from online search from internet & also from CD-ROM databases of the university library Rs. 2/- per A-4 size page shall be charged.

12. Information sources used by both university library users

A question was asked to know sources of information mostly used by respondents. The options were given as per available list of services given by UGC-Infonet digital library consortium. The responses were analyzed and presented in table no.02

Sr. No.	Services	Users in RTMNU Nagpur	Per. %	Users in SGBAU Amravati	Per. %
1)	Abstract	38	12.14	32	9.88
2)	Database search	43	13.74	49	15.12

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3)	Full text	59	18.85	55	16.98
4)	Hard copy	03	0.96	04	1.23
5)	Table of contents	09	2.87	14	4.32
6)	User login	02	0.64	03	0.93
7)	Publishers journals	31	9.90	37	11.42
8)	Publishers list	24	7.67	29	8.95
9)	Subject journal list	39	12.46	42	12.96
10)	Subject	20	6.39	14	4.32
11)	Journal list	26	8.31	27	8.33
12)	Table of content(archives)	15	4.79	13	4.01
13)	Print services	04	1.28	05	1.55
	Total	313	100	324	100

Table no. 02 Sources of information used by respondents

Figure no. 01 Sources of information used by respondents

(RTMNU- RashtrasantTukdojiMaharaj Nagpur University Nagpur)

(SGBAU- SantGadge Baba Amravati University Amravati)

Majority of users use as a source to 'full text' electronic journals and then use 'database search' from above options.

13. User's opinions of both universities about UGC-Infonet program

User's opinions are the most important things in the research to fulfill the objectives. The four options were given i.e. excellent, good, satisfactory and non-satisfactory. The responses were given by users analyzed and presented in table no.03

Sr. No.	Opinion	Users in RTMNU Nagpur	Per. %	Users in SGBAU Amravati	Per. %
01	Excellent	18	29.51	08	12.91
02	Good	32	52.46	43	69.35
03	Satisfactory	11	18.03	11	17.74
04	Non satisfactory	0	0.00	0	0.00
	Total	61	100	62	100

Table no. 03 Users opinions of both universities

Figure no. 02 Users opinions of both universities

Maximum library users of Rashtrasant Tukdoji Maharaj Nagpur University Nagpur opined that UGC Infonet e-journal consortium is 'Good' and Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University Amravati library user's also opined UGC Infonet e-journal consortium is 'good'.

14. Fulfillment level of users' needs

It is important to know the fulfillment of respondents by services of UGC-Infonet consortium. The four options were given as, fully, partially, up to some extent, very low extent. The data provided by respondents analyzed and presented in table no. 04

Sr.No.	Fulfillment level	Users in RTMNU Nagpur	Per. %	Users in SGBAU Amravati	Per. %
01	Fully	17	27.42	21	30.88
02	Partially	37	59.68	43	63.24
03	Up to some extent	07	11.29	03	4.41
04	Very low extent	01	1.61	01	1.47
	Total	62	100	68	100

Table no. 04 Level of fulfillment of users' needs

Figure no. 03 Level of fulfillment of users' needs

Majority of university library users fulfill their needs 'partially' in Rashtrasant Tukdoji Maharaj Nagpur University Nagpur and also in Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University Amravati.

15. Category of Users

A question was asked to respondents to know their general information. It helps to understand the user's category from total collected questionnaires. It is collected by the respondents were analyzed and presented in table no. 05

Sr. No.	Users Category	Users in RTMNU Nagpur	Per. %	Users in SGBAU Amravati	Per. %
01	Teachers	21	34.42	20	32.79
02	Researchers	20	32.79	20	32.79
03	PG students	20	32.79	21	34.42
	Total	61	100	61	100

Table no. 05 Category of users

Figure no. 04 Category of users

It is notable that the majority of users familiar with UGC-Infonet digital library consortium.

16. Frequency of internet access

This question was posed to respondents about the frequency of internet access. Six options are given and to mark of their choices. The options include more than one time in a day, once in a day, at least once in a week, at least once in a fortnight, once in a month. The data collected from the users were analyzed and presented in table no. 06

Sr. No.	Internet access frequency	Users in RTMNU Nagpur	Per. %	Users in SGBAU Amravati	Per. %
01	More than one time in a day	28	34.57	30	37.98
02	Once in a day	26	32.10	24	30.37
03	At least once in a week	13	16.05	08	10.14
04	At least once in fortnight	09	11.11	11	13.92
05	Once in a month	05	6.17	06	07.59
06	Other	00	00	00	00
	Total	81	100	79	100

Table no. 06 Frequency of internet access

Figure no. 05 Frequency of internet access

It is notable that maximum users used internet more than one time in every day.

17.Sources of information

The question was asked to the respondents about sources accepted to taking the information about use of UGC-Infonet digital library consortium. The ten options were given to respondents were analyzed and presented in table no. 07

Sr. No.	Sources of information	Users in RTMNU Nagpur	Per. %	Users in SGBAU Amravati	Per. %
01	Guidance from library staff	25	14.04	43	24.03
02	Help from friends/Colleagues	43	24.16	53	29.61
03	Through trial and error	53	29.79	55	30.73
04	Guidance from Guides /Teachers	04	02.24	12	06.72
05	From your co-researchers	16	08.98	08	04.48
06	Through user orientation program	04	02.24	03	
07	Through advertisement	25	14.05	02	1.13
08	From printed information about the consortium	03	01.68	02	1.13
09	Through training programme	04	02.25	01	00.57
10	Other sources	01	00.57	00	00
	Total	178	100	179	100

Table no. 07 Sources of information

Figure no. 06 Sources of information

Majority of users accepted the way through trial and error, and secondly help from friends/colleagues.

18. Use of e-resources for study/research of UGC-Infonet project

A question was asked to the respondents about the use of e-resources of UGC-Infonet consortium. The five options were given to the respondents. The responses were given by respondents analyzed and presented in table no. 08

Sr. No.	Use of e-resources	Users in RTMNU Nagpur	Per. %	Users in SGBAU Amravati	Per. %
01	E-journals	59	42.45	61	44.53
02	E-databases	45	32.37	54	39.42
03	E-books	27	19.42	17	12.41
04	Portals	06	04.32	05	03.65
05	Others	02	01.44	00	00
	Total	139	100	137	100

Table no. 08E-resources use for study/research of UGC-Infonet

Figure no. 07 E-resources use for study/research of UGC-Infonet

A large percentage of users said e-journals used for their subject study and research more than other e-sources.

19. Conclusion:-

It is evaluated that UGC Infonet digital library consortium avails thirteen different options to use e-resources. Maximum users use full text rather than other sources and fulfill their needs 'partially' in both universities. Maximum library

users of both universities opined that UGC Infonet e-journal consortium is 'Good'. It is notable that the majority of users familiar with UGC-Infonet digital library consortium and used internet more than one time in every day. Majority of users accepted the way through trial and error, and secondly help from friends/colleagues for searching e-resources first time. A large percentage of users said e-journals used for their subject study and research more than other e-sources.

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